

Comparative Analysis of Analogue to Digital Transition in Radio Broadcasting: A Case Study of Two Radio Stations in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT:

This paper presents a comparative analysis of analogue to digital transition in radio broadcasting with two radio stations (one private-owned and one federal government-owned) used as a case study. The two stations are located in Ikeja, Lagos State, Nigeria. Data was gotten from primary and secondary sources; that is from the equipment inventory logbooks of the stations and from the website of the International Telecommunication Union. The obtained data was analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) to find the relationship between the existing digital equipment and required digital equipment for transition from analogue to digital radio broadcasting. The findings of the data analysis carried out showed that there is positive relationship between the existing digital equipment and required digital equipment for digital radio broadcasting in both stations as $r = 0.9441$. Since the obtained value of r for both stations was less than 1, the number of existing digital broadcast equipment did not match the required number but are more than average to start digital radio broadcasting. Furthermore, both stations possess satisfactory number of analogue and digital equipment. Thus, both equipment can be utilized together for first level transition to digital radio broadcast until the analogue equipment are phased out.

Keywords: Digital equipment, Analogue equipment, Radio broadcasting, Comparative analysis, Transition.

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INTRODUCTION

The background to the transition from analogue to digital broadcasting began in the 1980s to 1990s when digital technologies began to surface and gained popularity. Since then, digital transformation has improved drastically and driven by advances in computing, adoption of sophisticated equipment and efficient electromagnetic spectrum. In analogue radio broadcasting, limited number of radio frequency spectrums are available which leads to congestion and interference among radio stations' frequencies. Therefore, the world has come up with wonderful and life-changing technological breakthroughs that offer migration to digital radio broadcasting so as to free up spectrum for use by mobile broadband and wireless services. This development led many advanced countries to launch commercial digital services in year 2000 with widespread adoption of digital service in year 2010 given the deadline for analogue radio switch off [1]. Many developed nations have seen a sharp increase in inventive capabilities across their economies, including the broadcast media sector, since the launch of digital radio services. By enabling a major change during the past 20 years, this technological advancement gave the broadcast media industry a foundation for growth [2].

Limited spectrum, poor sound reception, and signal interference are the hallmarks of analogue broadcasting. On the other hand, the digital broadcast provides cheaper maintenance, better transmission, less energy consumption, and an enhanced audience viewing or listening experience [3].

Despite series of deadlines given by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), Nigeria (that is radio stations in the country) failed to meet these deadlines set by ITU for a complete transition of all broadcast stations from analogue to digital transmission. In Nigeria, pay-digital terrestrial radio and internet radio have been deployed as substitutes to total transition of broadcast stations to digital broadcasting. The cost of acquiring the required broadcast equipment has been fingered as one of the many challenges confronting the total transition from analogue radio to digital transmission. Nigeria must strive to acquire and utilize the state-of-the-art digital broadcast equipment so as not to be left behind. Anything short of this will spell doom for the country's broadcasting operations [1,4].

Nigeria has over one hundred and fifty-five analogue radio stations mostly operating on a regional state basis and they all need serious investment for a complete switchover to digital transmission. This switchover to digital transmission requires the efforts of industry players. In one hand, financial investment on media transmission and production equipment that suite digital transmission is required. This means that broadcast stations must commit heavy capital to acquisition of broadcast equipment. On the other hand, the switchover to digital transmission would mean the audience would have to buy digital radio sets after the switchover [1].

In recent years, there have been concern among broadcast engineers and broadcast industry players about the preparedness of most radio broadcast stations to transit from analogue to digital transmission due to moribund broadcast equipment. Despite how crucial it is to transition from analog to digital broadcast operations, most broadcast stations lack the necessary broadcast equipment for the changeover. Private broadcast stations are more equipped than public radio in terms of availability of digital broadcast equipment. Therefore, since it has become obligatory that the country's broadcast media must transit from analogue broadcasting to digital system, transiting to digital radio broadcast has remained a big problem to most broadcast stations in Nigeria, especially in terms of procuring standard broadcast equipment that meets specification [4,5].

In view of the above, upgrading broadcast equipment from analogue to digital can be expensive for broadcasters. Thus, getting to know the required broadcast equipment to acquire for transition from analogue to digital radio broadcast has been one issue that has limited most public and private radio stations in Nigeria from transiting from analogue to digital transmission. The majority of media

outlets, both federal and private, have not yet integrated digital transmission into their daily broadcast. It might also be the apparent discrepancy in digital broadcast compliance between federal government-owned media organizations and commercial media outlets [5]. Thus, in this study, Pearson correlation coefficient will be utilized in analyzing the transition from analogue to digital radio broadcasting, and two stations are used as a case study. The aim is to check if the stations meet the requirement for transition from analogue to digital radio broadcasting.

SURVEY OF RELATED STUDIES

The study carried out by [6] found out that Nigeria is yet to match the technological advancement of developed nations to actualize the potentials of full digitization, and the study focus was on TV (television) stations. While [5] utilized empirical research approach to arrive at the conclusion that broadcast stations in Nigeria are ready for digital broadcasting but the scope of the readiness was not stated. In contrast to the findings done by [5], [2] concluded that digitalization of broadcasting (Radio and TV inclusive) in Nigeria is low and thus, does not meet ITU set standard for switchover to full digitalization. Furthermore, [7] assessed the preparedness of TV stations for digital broadcasting from existing literature. So, no quantitative research was conducted. Meanwhile, [1] identified policy formulation and implementation towards digitalization in Nigeria while [4] analyzed the varied problems faced by broadcast practitioners in relation with digital broadcasting in Uyo, Akwa-Ibom State. The author [8] on the other hand, compared the benefits and challenges of digital broadcasting in Nigeria.

It is evident from the reviewed works that analogue broadcasting is no more fashionable because it requires high bandwidth to broadcast analogue signals. It is also notable that the various stations in developing countries like Nigeria have not been able to completely switchover from analogue to digital broadcasting as a result of the huge financial investment needed for the acquisition of the necessary digital broadcast equipment. In broadcast stations where few broadcast equipment is available, most of them are either moribund or are not up to the standard specified by ITU. More studies are thus needed on the aspect of assessment of analogue to digital transition in radio broadcasting in Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

This study utilized onsite data collection as well as desk research design method. In the later method, existing data can be obtained from a variety of sources like websites, official books, periodicals and journals of an organization as well as government statistics.

Sources of Data

1. Primary data: these are those data collected from the field. Primary data was gotten from the equipment inventory logbooks of the selected radio stations. The obtained data are the number of existing analogue and digital broadcast equipment available in the two radio stations. Tables 1 and 2 shows the list of analogue and digital broadcast equipment in the selected radio stations, and this data was obtained in June 2024.

Table 1. List of Analogue Equipment in the Two Radio Stations

S/N.	Name of Analogue Broadcast Equipment	Specification	Available at the Private Station	Available at the Public Station
1.	Analogue Audio Processors		2	2
2.	Analogue transmitter	Minimum of 3.5kW	1	2
3.	Microphone	Multidirectional	6	5
4.	Unidirectional Antenna	3/5.5 decibel amplify	6	6
5.	Computer System	500GB, 12GB RAM	17	20
6.	Analogue Mixer/Console		2	2

7.	Analogue Oscilloscope		2	2
8.	Analogue frequency Analyser		2	2
9.	Studio Link (STL)		2	2
	Total		40	43

Table 2. List of Digital Broadcast Equipment in the Two Radio Stations

S/N.	Name of Digital Broadcast Equipment	Specification	Available at the Private Station	Available at the Public Station
1.	Broadcast studio automation server	1TB, 12GB RAM	2	1
2.	Broadcast digital Transmitter	Minimum of 5kW	1	1
3.	Digital Microphone		6	5
4.	All directions (multi-directional) antenna	3/5.5 decibel amplify	3	2
5.	Computer System (Laptop)	500 GB, 12GB RAM	12	15
6.	3/5.5 decibel amplify			
7.	Repeater Receive Antenna	100-152MHz	2	2
8.	Repeater Receive Antenna	100-163MHz	2	2
9.	Repeater Receive Antenna	100-172MHz	2	2
10.	Digital DMR standard repeater	Power (1-50W), Frequency Range (100-174 MHz)	5	6
11.	Digital Console		3	2
12.	Audio Processor		2	2
13.	Mobile DMR standard digital radio	With frequency range 100-174 MHz and GPS data transmit/receive	5	3
14.	Coaxial cable x 700m	50Ω high-resistance (RG213/U)	5	5
15.	Connectors	N Female connector type for RG 8/U coax	50	45
	Connectors	Male connector type for RG 8/U BNC	30	35
	Connectors	Male connector type for RG 8/U coax	20	15
16.	Multiplexer		0	0
17.	Mobile Programming Cable (Control head Connection)		0	0
18.	Mobile Programming Cable (Rear Connection)		0	0
19.	Repeater Programming Cable		0	0
20.	RDAC Software CD		0	0
21.	PS/Tuner DVD EMEA		0	0
22.	Streaming Software CD		1	1
	Total		151	144

2. Secondary data: these are data collected from non-primary sources. In this study, data was retrieved from the website of the ITU. Tables 3 and 4 shows the list of analogue and digital radio equipment as recommended by ITU for analogue and digital radio broadcasting respectively.

Table 3. List of ITU Recommended Analogue Broadcast Equipment

S/N.	Name of Broadcast Equipment	Specification	ITU recommended analogue equipment (minimum required number)
1.	Analogue Audio Processors		2
2.	Analogue transmitter	Minimum of 3.5kW	2
3.	Microphone	Multi-directional	6
4.	Unidirectional Antenna	3/5.5 decibel amplify	6
5.	Computer System	500GB, 12GB RAM	22
6.	Analogue Mixer/Console		2

7.	Analogue Oscilloscope		2
8.	Analogue frequency Analyser		2
9.	Studio Link (STL)		2
	Total		46

Source: [9]

Note: The data was accessed from [9] on June 2024. Thus, the data and link may have been updated since then or moved.

Table 4. List of ITU Recommended Digital Broadcast Equipment

S/N.	Name of Broadcast Equipment	Specification	Minimum number of digital equipment recommended by ITU
1	Broadcast studio automation server	1TB, 12GB RAM	3
2	Broadcast digital Transmitter	Minimum of 5kW	2
3	Digital Microphone		12
4	All directions (multi-directional) antenna		4
5	Computer System (Laptop)	500 GB, 12GB RAM	22
6	3/5.5 decibel amplify		
7	Repeater Receive Antenna	100-152MHz	8
8	Repeater Receive Antenna	100-163MHz	8
9	Repeater Receive Antenna	100-152MHz	8
10	Digital DMR standard repeater	Power (1-50W), Frequency Range (100-174 MHz)	12
11	Digital Console		4
12	Audio Processor		5
13	Mobile DMR standard digital radio	With frequency range 100-174 MHz and GPS data transmit/receive	
14	Coaxial cable x 700m	50Ω high-resistance (RG213/U)	
15	Connectors	N Female connector type for RG 8/U coax	many
	Connectors	N Male connector type for RG 8/U BNC	many
	Connectors	Male connector type for RG 8/U coax	many
16	Multiplexer		
17	Mobile Programming Cable (Control head Connection)		1
18	Mobile Programming Cable (Rear Connection)		1
19	Repeater Programming Cable		1
20	RDAC Software CD		1
21	PS/Tuner DVD EMEA		1
22	Streaming Software CD		1
	Total		94

Source: [9]

Note: The data was accessed from [9] on June 2024. Thus, the data and link may have been updated since then or moved.

Tables 5 and 6 shows the combined list of analogue and digital equipment in both radio stations with that of the ITU.

Table 5. Analogue Broadcast Equipment in the Selected Broadcast Stations with ITU's Recommended Analogue Broadcast Equipment

S/N	Name of Broadcast Equipment	Specification	Available at the Private Station	Available at the Public Station	No. of analogue equipment recommended by ITU
1.	Analogue Audio Processors		2	2	2

2.	Analogue transmitter	Minimum of 3.5kW	1	2	2
3.	Microphone	Multidirectional	6	5	6
4.	Unidirectional Antenna	3/5.5 decibel amplify	6	6	6
5.	Computer System	500GB, 12GB RAM	17	20	22
6.	Analogue Mixer/Console		2	2	2
7.	Analogue Oscilloscope		2	2	2
8.	Analogue frequency Analyser		2	2	2
9.	Studio Link (STL)		2	2	2
	Total		40	43	46

Table 6. Digital Broadcast Equipment in the Selected Broadcast Stations with ITU's Recommended Digital Broadcast Equipment

S/N.	Name of Broadcast Equipment	Specification	Available at Star FM	Available at Bond FM	ITU Recommended
1.	Broadcast studio automation server	1TB, 12GB RAM	2	1	3
2.	Broadcast digital transmitter	Minimum of 5kW	1	1	2
3.	Digital Microphone		6	5	12
4.	All directions (multidirectional) antenna	3/5.5 decibel amplify	3	2	4
5.	Computer System (Laptop)	500 GB, 12GB RAM	12	15	22
6.	3/5.5 decibel amplifier		0	0	0
7.	Repeater Receive Antenna	100-152MHz	2	2	8
8.	Repeater Receive Antenna	100-163MHz	2	2	8
9.	Repeater Receive Antenna	100-172MHz	2	2	8
10.	Digital DMR standard repeater	Power (1-50W), Frequency Range (100-174MHz)	5	6	12
11.	Digital Console		3	2	4
12.	Audio Processor		2	2	5
13.	Mobile DMR standard digital radio	With frequency range 100-174 MHz and GPS data transmit/receive	5	3	0
14.	Coaxial cable x 700m	50Ω high-resistance (RG213/U)	5	5	0
15.	Connectors	N Female connector type for RG 8/U coaxial	50	45	many
	Connectors	N Male connector type for RG 8/U BNC	30	35	many
	Connectors	Male connector type for RG 8/U coaxial	20	15	Many
16.	Multiplexer		0	0	0
17.	Mobile Programming Cable (Control head Connection)		0	0	1
18.	Mobile Programming Cable (Rear Connection)		0	0	1
19.	Repeater Programming Cable		0	0	1
20.	RDAC Software CD		0	0	1
21.	PS/Tuner DVD EMEA		0	0	1
22.	Streaming Software CD		1	1	1
	Total		151	144	94

Population of the Study

These are all terrestrial radio broadcast stations in Nigeria. Data was obtained from the equipment inventory logbooks of the two stations as a subset of the terrestrial radio broadcast stations in Nigeria.

Sample Size

This was chosen in this study to represent the whole population of all radio broadcast stations in Nigeria. The sample size is the two radio stations located in Ikeja, Lagos comprising one public and one private broadcast radio station.

Data Analysis Framework

Descriptive statistics was used to statistically analyze data from the radio stations. Pearson Correlation Coefficient was used to test a line relationship between two variables. Thus, the line relationship between the existing broadcast equipment of the radio stations and the recommended broadcast equipment by ITU would be analyzed using Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r). The obtained results will be used to assess the readiness of each of the broadcast station for transition from analogue to digital broadcast. The Pearson Correlation Coefficient states thus [10]:

$$r = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (1)$$

Where r = Correlation Coefficient; x = for this study, it is the list of existing digital equipment in each of the selected radio stations; y = for this study, it is the list of recommended and specified digital broadcast equipment by the ITU; x_i = value of x variables in a sample; y_i = value of y variables in a sample; \bar{x} = mean of the values of x variables and \bar{y} = mean of the values of y variables.

The decision rules with respect to r , are:

1. If $r = 0$, then the station cannot transit from analogue to digital broadcasting because the result indicates there is no relationship between the equipment on ground in the station and the recommended equipment by ITU. It shows that the station makes no effort to transit from analogue to digital radio broadcast.
2. If $0 < r \leq 0.4990$, the station's list of equipment is less than average and cannot kick start digitalized radio transmission. The value in this range indicates the station makes efforts to go digital but the available equipment does not meet the recommended equipment number.
3. If $0.5 \geq r \leq 0.999$, then the digital broadcast equipment list in the station is yet to meet up with the expected number of digital equipment but the list is more than average for the station to begin the process of digital radio transmission with the few available digital equipment.
4. If $r = 1$, the coefficient value of 1 indicates that the number of each of the required and specified broadcast equipment meet the expectations of ITU as recommended and the station can go on full digital radio transmission.

RESULTS

Correlation Data Analysis

In this analysis, X and A are independent variables and are the values of the list of digital equipment in the private and public stations in Lagos. Y is the list of recommended digital broadcast equipment by ITU for easy transition to digital radio broadcasting. This analysis is necessary to ascertain the readiness of the stations for digital transition.

In order to obtain accurate results, 3/5.5 decibel amplifier, Mobile DMR standard digital radio, Coaxial cable x 700m, multiplexer and the three connectors type will not be considered because they have

no numeric (non-zero) values as seen from the ITU column in Table 6. The correlation data analysis of the private and public radio stations are shown in Tables 7 and 8 respectively.

Table 7. Correlation Data Analysis for the Private Radio Station’s Digital Equipment List (X) with ITU Standard Equipment (Y)

X	Y	$p = x_i - \bar{x}$	$q = y_i - \bar{y}$	p^2	q^2	pq
2	3	-0.4118	-2.5294	0.1696	6.3979	1.0416
1	2	-1.4118	-3.5294	1.9932	12.4567	4.9828
6	12	3.5882	6.4706	12.8752	41.8687	23.2178
3	4	0.5882	-1.5294	0.3460	2.3391	-0.8996
12	22	9.5882	16.4706	91.9336	271.2807	157.9234
2	8	-0.4118	2.4706	0.1696	6.1039	-1.0174
2	8	-0.4118	2.4706	0.1696	6.1039	-1.0174
2	8	-0.4118	2.4706	0.1696	6.1039	-1.0174
5	12	2.5882	6.4706	6.6988	41.8687	16.7472
3	4	0.5882	-1.5294	0.3460	2.3391	-0.8996
2	5	-0.4118	-0.5294	0.1696	0.2803	0.2180
0	1	-2.4118	-4.5294	5.8168	20.5155	10.9240
0	1	-2.4118	-4.5294	5.8168	20.5155	10.9240
0	1	-2.4118	-4.5294	5.8168	20.5155	10.9240
0	1	-2.4118	-4.5294	5.8168	20.5155	10.9240
0	1	-2.4118	-4.5294	5.8168	20.5155	10.9240
1	1	-1.4118	-4.5294	1.9932	20.5155	6.3946
41	94	-0.0006	0.0002	146.1180	520.2359	260.2940

Mean (\bar{x}) = $\frac{\sum fX}{n}$, where n = 17. Therefore, $\bar{x} = \frac{41}{17} = 2.4118$

Mean (\bar{y}) = $\frac{\sum fY}{n}$, where n = 17. Therefore, $\bar{y} = \frac{94}{17} = 5.5294$

The Pearson Correlation Coefficient thus is:

$$r = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2}} = \frac{260.2940}{\sqrt{146.1180 * 520.2359}} = \frac{260.2940}{\sqrt{76015.82924}} = \frac{260.2940}{275.7096829} = 0.9441$$

Table 8. Correlation Data Analysis for the Public Radio Station’s Digital Equipment List (A) with ITU Standard Equipment (Y)

A	Y	$m = a_i - \bar{a}$	$q = y_i - \bar{y}$	m^2	q^2	mq
2	3	-0.4118	-2.5294	0.1696	6.3979	1.0416
1	2	-1.4118	-3.5294	1.9932	12.4567	4.9828
6	12	3.5882	6.4706	12.8752	41.8687	23.2178
3	4	0.5882	-1.5294	0.3460	2.3391	-0.8996
12	22	9.5882	16.4706	91.9336	271.2807	157.9234
2	8	-0.4118	2.4706	0.1696	6.1039	-1.0174
2	8	-0.4118	2.4706	0.1696	6.1039	-1.0174
2	8	-0.4118	2.4706	0.1696	6.1039	-1.0174
5	12	2.5882	6.4706	6.6988	41.8687	16.7472
3	4	0.5882	-1.5294	0.3460	2.3391	-0.8996
2	5	-0.4118	-0.5294	0.1696	0.2803	0.2180
0	1	-2.4118	-4.5294	5.8168	20.5155	10.9240
0	1	-2.4118	-4.5294	5.8168	20.5155	10.9240
0	1	-2.4118	-4.5294	5.8168	20.5155	10.9240
0	1	-2.4118	-4.5294	5.8168	20.5155	10.9240
0	1	-2.4118	-4.5294	5.8168	20.5155	10.9240
1	1	-1.4118	-4.5294	1.9932	20.5155	6.3946
41	94	-0.0006	0.0002	146.1180	520.2359	260.2940

Mean (\bar{a}) = $\frac{\sum fA}{n}$, where n = 17. Therefore, $\bar{a} = \frac{41}{17} = 2.4118$

Mean (\bar{y}) = $\frac{\sum fY}{n}$, where n = 17. Therefore, $\bar{y} = \frac{94}{17} = 5.5294$

The Pearson Correlation Coefficient thus is:

$$r = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2}} = \frac{260.2940}{\sqrt{146.1180 * 520.2359}} = \frac{260.2940}{\sqrt{76015.82924}} = \frac{260.2940}{275.7096829} = 0.9441$$

Coincidentally, the result of the Pearson Correlation coefficient, r in this case is also 0.9441.

DISCUSSION

For the private radio station: the result of the Pearson Correlation coefficient, r is 0.9441. The digital equipment list in any broadcast station must be directly proportional to the recommended equipment list by ITU for full digitalization of such broadcast station. Therefore, in this scenario, the constant, r, which forms the relationship between the variables must be 1. Since

$$X \propto Y \quad (2)$$

$$X = rY \quad (3)$$

Thus, as seen for the private radio station, r = 0.9441. Implying that X=0.9441Y.

As the values of each of the required equipment increases, the value of r increases until the point where r = 1. At r = 1 is the point at which the total sum of the broadcast equipment in a station equals the sum total of required or recommended broadcast equipment by the ITU. Thus, at r = 0.9441, using the decision rules, the value of r is less than 1 but greater than 0.5. This apparently shows that the overall digital equipment list in the private radio station is not up to the required or specified number but are still good enough to kick start transition from analogue to digital radio broadcasting.

For the public radio station:

$$A \propto Y \quad (4)$$

$$A = rY \quad (5)$$

Thus, as seen for the public radio station, r = 0.9441. Implying that A=0.9441Y. This also shows that the overall digital equipment list in the station is not up to the required or specified number but are still good enough to kick start transition from analogue to digital radio broadcasting.

CONCLUSION

It is evident from the results of the comparative analysis that the two radio stations have invested huge number of resources in acquiring some digital broadcast equipment, even if the available equipment is yet to meet the required number. Furthermore, in line with the quantitative data collected from the international telecommunication union's website and equipment inventory logbooks of the selected radio stations; the equipment list in both stations is positively related to the required equipment recommended by ITU as $r = 0.9441$ from the analysis carried out for the two stations. Thus, since the values of r for both stations fall within the range of $0 < r < 1$, it implies that both radio stations have made effort in acquiring the required digital broadcast equipment but the

available equipment are yet to meet the standard for full digital radio broadcasting. This study thus adds to the body of knowledge as it offers insights that facilitate the transition from analogue to digital broadcasting, and by exploring the content of this study, researchers and broadcasters in developing countries can advance their knowledge on transition from analogue to digital radio broadcasting.

Furthermore, in light of the results of this study, the following suggestions are noteworthy for radio broadcast stations in Nigeria:

1. They should explore other options of acquiring new digital broadcast equipment through equipment leasing or renting due to high cost of outright purchase of new equipment for transition to digital radio broadcast.
2. They should identify the gap between their existing analogue equipment and the required digital equipment for digital radio broadcasting to determine the equipment that is needed to meet the set standards.
3. They could use their existing analogue equipment side by side with their available digital broadcast equipment and gradually phase out the utilization of the analogue equipment starting from the most critical to the least until all the analogue broadcast equipment are totally replaced.

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